

FATIGUE BEHAVIOUR OF A COMPOSITE FOR AUTOMOTIVE APPLICATION: STUDY OF A FIBREGLASS FABRIC REINFORCED THERMOPLASTIC POLYMER

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ABSTRACT

This study is focused on the tensile-tensile fatigue behaviour of a woven glass-fibre-reinforced composite with polyamide 6,6 resin. As a preliminary step, material integrity has been investigated using tomography technique. Moreover, mechanical properties of the material have been determined through static tensile test. Two layups have been deeply studied, referred as $[(0/90)_3]$ and $[(\pm 45)_3]$ in order to study the influence of fibre orientation in the material. An optimisation step has been necessary to revise the coupon geometry for fatigue tests. Dogbone specimens have been developed in that purpose, leading to the coupon failure in the gauge section. The S-N curves of both composites have been established at a stress ratio (R) of 0.1. These curves have been used as the basis for the identification of two fatigue life models: a model based on constant life diagrams and a two material parameters model. S-N curve for the $[(\pm 45)_3]$ composite has been used to validate the latter. Fatigue tests were multi-instrumented using infrared camera and acoustic emission monitoring to determine the maximum temperature and the cumulated number of events. Together with the secant modulus evolution, these three parameters are good indicators of the damage level in the composite. Finally, post-mortem SEM observations have been carried out in order to identify damage mechanisms which take place into the composite during fatigue tests.

1 INTRODUCTION

Glass-fibre-reinforced composite with thermoplastic matrix are of interest when it comes to lightening of automotive structural parts. Several authors have studied the fatigue behaviour of such composites, either with short fibres [1–3] or woven fabric [4, 5]. Concerning the fatigue behaviour of woven composite, the earlier damage mechanism identified is fibre-matrix debonds leading to the cracking of transverse yarn [6]. Then, when the transverse crack has reached the edge of the yarn, either it propagates into a matrix-rich area or it is deflected into the adjacent longitudinal yarn, which is called meta-delamination [7]. Lastly, the final failure of the material is always the result of catastrophic failure of the longitudinal fibres. The aim of this study is to characterise the purely tensile fatigue behaviour of a woven glass-fibre-reinforced composite with a polyamide 6,6 matrix. First, the static mechanical properties have been determined using rectangular coupons. This type of specimen cannot be used for fatigue tests since it leads to the systematic failure of the coupon into the grip, making the test non-valid. Thus, a dogbone specimen has been developed to achieve fatigue tests. This study makes possible the construction of Wöhler curves for two composites layups: $[(0/90)_3]$ and $[(\pm 45)_3]$. Damage mechanisms are studied using different methods: infrared camera cartography, acoustic emission monitoring and post-mortem microscopic observations. Finally, the experimental data have been used to identify two fatigue life models.

2 MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Tested Material

The studied composite material is made of 3 plies of a 2/2 twill woven glass fabric impregnated with polyamide 6,6 resin. The influence of fabric orientation on mechanical properties is studied using three different composites. The first one, referred as $[(0/90)_3]$, has the warp direction of each ply oriented à 0° from the tensile axis (x axis). The second one, referred as $[(\pm 45)_3]$, has the warp direction of each ply oriented alternately at $+45^\circ$ and -45° from the tensile axis. Finally, the third one, referred as $[(90/0)_3]$, has the weft direction of each ply oriented à 0° from the tensile axis. This last composite is supposed to have the same mechanical properties as the $[(0/90)_3]$ composite, thus it has not been deeply explored. The void content into the resin has been investigated by using micro-tomography technique. It has been found lower than 1% and randomly distributed into the material (Figure 1).

Figure 1: Micro-tomography scans of pristine $[(0/90)_3]$ specimen (resolution $18\mu\text{m}$).

Two specimen geometries have been used in this study. For static tests, rectangular coupons with the dimensions of 200 mm x 20 mm x 1,53 mm have been cut in composite plates. Rectangular specimens have exhibited systematic failure into the grips during fatigue tests. Thus, dogbone specimen has been developed in order to secure the failure in the centre of the specimen. The specificity of this specimen is the non-constant gauge section introduced through a well-chosen radius of curvature. This radius has been determined in order to create a stress concentration factor in the centre of the specimen higher than the one induced by the grip. This optimized geometry has the same gauge section in the centre than the rectangular specimen and has been used for all fatigue tests.

2.2 Experimental Procedure

Static tensile tests were performed by using an INSTRON 4505 electromechanical machine with a cross-head speed of 1 mm/min and strain was measured by a 25 mm extensometer. The fatigue tests were performed with an INSTRON 8501 servo-hydraulic machine. Constant amplitude loads were applied in a sinusoidal waveform at the frequency of 1 Hz under load control, in tensile loading exclusively, and with a fatigue stress ratio (R) of 0.1. The secant modulus was calculated as the difference between maximum and minimum stress divided by the difference between maximum and minimum cross-head position. Fatigue tests were stopped at specimen failure or when reached 10^6 cycles. In order to detail analysis of the damage process, the mechanical tests were multi-instrumented. In situ measurements were carried out by using acoustic emission (AE) monitoring and infrared camera. After fatigue tests, scanning electron microscopy (SEM) have been carried out on specimens fracture surface. The acoustic emission monitoring was performed by using the AE system from Physical Acoustic SA. Two sensors (Micro80) were placed at the gauge extremities, with a distance of 100 mm between their centres. The amplitude threshold has been chosen equal to 35 dB. An infrared camera from Cedip Infrared Systems with a detector resolution of $90\mu\text{m}/\text{pixel}$ was used to measure the temperature evolution at the surface of specimens during fatigue tests.

2.3 Data Analysis

S-N curves have been analysed by using two fatigue life models. The first one is developed by Vassilopoulos et al. [8] and deals with the construction of constant life diagrams. These diagrams are predictive tools for the estimation of the fatigue life under experimental conditions for which no experimental data exist. From one S-N curve plotted for a R-value in the range [0 ; 1], it is possible to build the CLD diagram for all values of R from 0 to 1. CLD diagrams are obtained by plotting σ_a against R or against σ_m using Equation 1.

$$\sigma_a = \frac{1 - R}{A_{III}R^n + B_{III}} \quad (1)$$

with:

$$\begin{cases} A_{III} = \frac{2}{\sigma_0} - \frac{1}{\sigma_a^{R=0}} \\ B_{III} = \frac{1}{\sigma_a^{R=0}} \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

where σ_0 is the ultimate tensile strength of the material and $\sigma_a^{R=0}$ the amplitude of the fatigue stress applied during a fatigue test at R = 0. If the experimental S-N curve available is plotted for R = 0.1, A_{III} and B_{III} can be calculated using Equation 3.

$$\begin{cases} A_{III} = \frac{2}{\sigma_0} - \left(\frac{1}{0,999} \left(\frac{0,9}{\sigma_a^{R=0,1}} - \frac{2 * 10^{-3}}{\sigma_0} \right) \right) \\ B_{III} = \frac{1}{0,999} \left(\frac{0,9}{\sigma_a^{R=0,1}} - \frac{2 * 10^{-3}}{\sigma_0} \right) \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

The second fatigue life model used in this study is proposed by Epaarachchi et al. [9] and has been widely used by other authors to model the behaviour of composite materials [10–13]. This predictive model takes into account the frequency, the stress ratio and the fibre orientation in the composite (Equation 4).

$$N_f = \left[1 + \left(\frac{\sigma_{0,\theta}}{\sigma_{max}} - 1 \right) \frac{f^\beta}{\alpha(1 - R)^{\lambda - R|\sin \theta|}} \left(\frac{\sigma_{0,\theta}}{\sigma_{max}} \right)^{\lambda - 1 - R|\sin \theta|} \right]^{\frac{1}{\beta}} \quad (4)$$

where σ_{max} is the maximum fatigue stress, $\sigma_{0,\theta}$ is the ultimate tensile strength, f is the frequency, R is the stress ratio, θ is the smallest angle of fibres between the loading direction and the fibre direction and α and β are material constants. In order to identify these two parameters, Equation 4 has to be written as Equation 5:

$$\alpha(N_f^\beta - 1) = \left(\frac{\sigma_{0,\theta}}{\sigma_{max}} - 1 \right) \frac{f^\beta}{(1 - R)^{1,6 - R|\sin \theta|}} \left(\frac{\sigma_{0,\theta}}{\sigma_{max}} \right)^{0,6 - R|\sin \theta|} \quad (5)$$

α and β have to be optimized in order to ensure that the experimental data converge on a straight line passing through the origin when plotting the right-hand term against $(N_f^\beta - 1)$.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Mechanical tests

3.1.1 Static Tests

Static tests have been carried out on both [(0/90)₃] and [(±45)₃] layup composites. Specimens were conditioned at ambient atmosphere and humidity. Results are shown in Figure 2. For the [(0/90)₃] composite, the ultimate tensile strength is equal to 318± 9MPa with a strain at break of 1.85±0.13%.

The Young modulus has been found equal to 18.3 ± 1.7 GPa. The stress-strain curve presents a “knee-point” at 0.4% strain, characteristic of the static behaviour of woven composite [14–16]. For the $[(\pm 45)_3]$ composite, the ultimate tensile strength is equal to 128 ± 5 MPa, with a strain at break of $17.7 \pm 1.2\%$. One can notice that this value is 10 times higher than the strain at break found for the $[(0/90)_3]$ composite. The Young modulus has been found equal to 5.00 ± 0.39 GPa.

Figure 2: Stress-strain curves for static tests on $[(0/90)_3]$ and $[(\pm 45)_3]$ coupons

3.1.2 Fatigue Tests

Fatigue tests have been carried out on six $[(0/90)_3]$ specimens at six different fatigue stress levels. Five $[(90/0)_3]$ specimens have been tested at similar fatigue stress levels to ensure their equivalence to the $[(0/90)_3]$ specimens. Finally, eleven $[(\pm 45)_3]$ specimens have been tested at five different fatigue stress levels in order to evaluate the results dispersion. All tested specimens were conditioned under the relative humidity content RH0 as defined by the standard ISO-1110. S-N curves for the two studied composites are presented in Figure 3.

Figure 3: S-N curves for $[(0/90)_3]$, $[(90/0)_3]$ and $[(\pm 45)_3]$ specimens. $R = 0.1$ and $f = 1$ Hz

The S-N curves both show that the fatigue life increases when the fatigue stress applied decreases. Two specimens did not break at 10^6 cycles, tests were then stopped and corresponding symbols are presented in Figure 3 with arrowhead. Repeatability study carried out on $[(\pm 45)_3]$ coupons shows a very small dispersion of the results.

3.1.3 Evolution of mechanical parameters

The normalised secant modulus has been studied during fatigue tests carried out on $[(0/90)_3]$ and $[(\pm 45)_3]$ composites. Results are plotted in Figure 4 versus the normalized number of cycles.

Figure 4: Evolution of the normalised secant modulus for $[(0/90)_3]$ and $[(\pm 45)_3]$ composites for three fatigue stress levels. $R = 0.1$ and $f = 1\text{Hz}$.

Three zones in the evolution of the normalized secant modulus can be determined from these graphs: zone I is characterized by a significant initial slope, then zone II shows a more gradual slope. Finally, zone III is described as the period just before the failure and is defined by a gradually decreasing slope. For $[(0/90)_3]$ composite, whatever the fatigue stress level applied, the evolution of the secant modulus is the same during the test. For $[(\pm 45)_3]$ composite, the duration of zone I increases with the fatigue stress applied.

3.1.4 Infrared measurements and acoustic emission

Fatigue tests have been multi-instrumented with infrared camera and acoustic emission device. The infrared camera allowed the study of the maximum surface temperature of the specimen during the test whereas the acoustic emission has been used to study the cumulated number of acoustic events.

Figure 5: Evolution of normalized temperature variation, cumulated number of acoustic events and secant modulus for $[(0/90)_3]$ and $[(\pm 45)_3]$ composites.

These two parameters are good indicators for the damage level of the composite, as well as the secant modulus. Figure 5 shows the evolution of these three normalized indicators against the normalized number of cycles for a high fatigue stress level applied (respectively 90% and 80% of the static strength for $[(0/90)_3]$ and $[(\pm 45)_3]$ composites). The three zones previously identified are clearly visible in Figure 5 with the same trends as described in paragraph 3.1.3. The duration of each zone seems to be dependent on the composite layup. It is worth noticing that in the case of a high fatigue stress applied, the temperature of $[(\pm 45)_3]$ specimen increases drastically (more than 40°C) and the temperature evolution does not exhibit a three zones evolution. This three steps evolution appears again when the applied stress decreases.

3.1.5 Microscopic observations

Post-mortem SEM observations have been carried out on the fracture surface of some metalized $[(0/90)_3]$ specimens (Figure 6). These observations have allowed highlighting damage mechanisms that occurred in these specimens during fatigue test.

Figure 6: SEM observations of fracture surface. (a) Fracture surface overview (b) Fibre-matrix debonds (c) Matrix cracking (d) Meta-delamination (e) Fibre pull-out.

One can notice fibre-matrix debonds into transverse yarns. Figure 6c shows a resin-rich area, with an initiation zone, probably due to the presence of a defect or a void in the matrix. The crack front is visible as well as a river-like pattern. Meta-delamination is noticeable in Figure 6d. This surface damage might be the result of the propagation of a transverse crack at the interface between a longitudinal and a transverse yarn. Finally, fibre pull-out phenomenon has been noticed on the fracture surface.

3.2 Fatigue life models

The model submitted by Vassilopoulos et al. [8] has been evaluated using Equation 1 and experimental data on [(0/90)₃] composite. From the unique S-N curve plotted at R = 0.1, it has been possible to build the CLD for the whole range of R from 0 to 1. CLD in the $\sigma^a - R$ and $\sigma^a - \sigma^m$ planes are presented in Figure 7. It is also possible to plot constant life diagrams in 3 dimensions as shown in Figure 8. This model needs to be validated by other experimental data obtained at different R-values.

Figure 7: Constant life diagrams in the planes ($\sigma^a - \sigma^m$) and ($\sigma^a - R$) for the [(0/90)₃] composite.

Figure 8: 3D representation of constant life diagram established for the [(0/90)₃] composite.

The model proposed by Epaarachchi et al. [9] requires an optimization step for the determination of material constants α and β . The optimisation scheme used is described by Figure 9. Firstly, β has to be set arbitrarily and used in Equation 5. The right-hand term of this equation, referred as “A”, has to be plot against $(N_f^\beta - 1)$: α is given by the slope of this curve. The couple of values ($\alpha ; \beta$) has to be optimised until this curve turn into a straight line passing through the origin (Figure 10).

Figure 9: Optimisation scheme for the determination of α and β .

Figure 10: Curve for the determination of material parameters α and β for the $[(0/90)_3]$ composite.

The identification of the material parameters has been done using the experimental data on the $[(0/90)_3]$ composite: α and β has been found to be equal respectively to 0.022 and 0.465. Then, the model and the material constants have been validated on the experimental data obtained on the $[(\pm 45)_3]$ composite (Figure 11). By simply changing the value of the ultimate tensile strength ($\sigma_{0,\theta}$) and the fiber orientation (θ), the calculated S-N curve shows a good fitting to the experimental data. Dotted lines indicated the dispersion of the model, based on the dispersion of the ultimate tensile strength values. Thus, this model has the main advantage to be predictive and relatively easy-to-fit.

Figure 11: Calculated and experimental S-N curves. (a) Identification on [(0/90)₃] composite.
(b) Validation on [(±45)₃] composite.

4 CONCLUSIONS

This study deals with the fatigue behaviour of a thermoplastic composite reinforced with a woven glass fabric. Two types of composite layups have been deeply studied: [(0/90)₃] and [(±45)₃]. Fatigue tests have been instrumented with infrared camera and acoustic emission device. These techniques allowed the control of the maximum surface temperature and the cumulated number of acoustic events during fatigue tests. Static tests have made possible the determination of mechanical properties such as the ultimate tensile strength, the strain at break and the Young modulus. The [(0/90)₃] composite have shown the presence of a “knee-point” at 0.4% strain, characteristic of the static behaviour of woven composites. The strain at break of the [(±45)₃] composite is ten times higher than the one determined on [(0/90)₃] composite because of the orientation of the fibres in the fabric. The damage features (surface temperature, cumulated number of acoustic events and secant modulus) have shown a three zones distribution. SEM observations have highlighted several damage mechanisms occurring during fatigue tests: fibre-matrix debonds, cracking in rich-matrix zones and delamination. Finally, S-N curves have been used to evaluate material parameters of two fatigue life models. The predictive model proposed by Epaarachchi et al. seems promising and show a good fitting to experimental data.

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